

ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN THE HALAL INDUSTRY OF BALKAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The halal industry in the Balkan countries is characterized by a blend of traditional and contemporary perceptions of halal. The halal market is defined by openness and inclusivity, allowing active participation of various stakeholders regardless of their religious affiliation. While the fundamental principles of halal are defined by halal standards, there are no predefined solutions for ethical questions and dilemmas. This paper presents five key dilemmas: a holistic understanding of halal, labelling and recognition of halal products, pricing, trust in non-Muslim producers, and halal product identity. The essence of each dilemma is explained and adopted solutions aimed at ensuring transparency, integrity, and reliability of halal products are presented. The conclusions emphasize the importance of continuous education and the need for clearly defining ethical norms as prerequisites for maintaining the integrity of halal and the trust of halal consumers.

Keywords: halal, ethical dilemmas, halal industry, Balkan countries

INTRODUCTION

The halal industry in the Balkan countries, in its current form, began its developmental journey in 2005 with the creation of the Bosnia-Herzegovinian standard BAS 1049 - Halal Food, Requirements, and Measures. In parallel with this process, the Islamic Community in Bosnia and Herzegovina initiated discussions about the certification system and the operational model of the halal industry, involving representatives from the industry, chambers of commerce, and academic institutions. The establishment of the Agency for Halal Quality Certification created the basic institutional framework, which progressively expanded from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia to other Balkan countries, including Serbia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, and other European countries. At the same time, the Agency played an active role in international standardization, accreditation, and the development of halal business operations.

The development of the halal industry in the Balkan region involved addressing various normative, organizational, religious, economic, cultural, market, and ethical issues and dilemmas. While the halal status of products and services are clearly defined by the halal standard, ethical issues do not have predefined and universally accepted solutions. Therefore, this paper pays particular attention to ethical dilemmas, as they significantly affect the perception of halal and trust in its integrity.

This paper focuses on five key ethical dilemmas that illustrate the complexity of halal. The identified dilemmas relate to a holistic view of understanding halal, the role of consumers, the recognition of halal products in the market, the pricing of halal products, and issues of halal integrity. In the discussion of ethical dilemmas in the Balkan halal industry, each aspect is illustrated with an appropriate example. The elaboration of these dilemmas and their resolution primarily relies on normative provisions of the halal standard BAS 1049, and other documents adopted by the Institute for Standardization and Metrology of Islamic Countries (SMIIC). However, despite the existence of agreed solutions for most of the dilemmas mentioned, these issues remain a subject of discussion due to differences in the understanding of halal, its religious and ethical principles, and the practice of halal certification.

Halal and Ethical Dilemmas Framework

In this paper, the term "halal industry" is used as a designation encompassing the production of halal products, the provision of halal services, and the halal certification system. In addition to "halal industry," recent literature also adopts terms such as *Halalonomics*, defined as the national system of the halal economy (Hodžić, 2022), and *halal ecosystem*, which includes Shari'ah-compliant financial instruments, fostering ethical practices, enhancing market reach, and ensuring business operations adhere to Islamic principles (Raimi et al., 2024).

Decision-making plays a central role in both classical and halal economies. It involves choosing between different alternatives, often addressing dilemmas with moral or societal implications. A dilemma is defined as "a choice between two or more alternatives in which the outcomes are equally undesirable or equally favourable" (LLC, 2024). Additionally, an *ethical dilemma* narrows this choice to decisions involving conflicting values and beliefs, where neither option is entirely acceptable from an ethical perspective (CFI Education, n.d.). In some interpretations, both choices may be morally unacceptable to the individual (Thpanorama, 2024). Unlike ethical dilemmas, ethical questions are less demanding as they focus primarily on whether something is ethically acceptable, where "the ethical course of action will be the 'least bad' option" (UKCEN, 2024). In comparison, they are generally less complex than dilemmas, which require decisions among multiple solutions that are equally acceptable or unacceptable.

Ethical dilemmas in theoretical discourse are classified as hypothetical, real, open, closed, completed, and incomplete. In the context of the halal industry, *real dilemmas* concern practical issues predominantly related to compliance with standards. On the other hand, *hypothetical dilemmas* are more common in academic discourse and literature, addressing situations that are unlikely to occur in real life (Sainte Anastasie, 2024). Ethical dilemmas are often fundamentally connected to cultural, traditional, religious, and spiritual values. Their interpretation is further influenced by general education levels, historical context, and sociological factors. Individuals

resolving ethical dilemmas, especially within the context of the halal industry, frequently face societal pressures, as their decisions are often judged by the public through different value perspectives.

This terminological framework provides a basis for analyzing the dilemmas faced by the halal industry and its consumers in navigating complex decisions while maintaining the integrity of halal principles.

Holistic Understanding of Halal

Halal is fundamentally a religious category, but over time, it has evolved to encompass various linguistic and cultural dimensions, becoming part of the traditions of many nations worldwide. In the Balkan traditions, halal is understood through four meanings: *food permissible for Muslims, fair earnings, forgiving an injustice or offense, and giving something for free as a gift*. This diversity of meanings has shaped halal into a concept that is now part of the shared linguistic heritage and culture of coexistence between Muslims and non-Muslims in the region.

Although halal is predominantly associated with food, in the modern context, it extends beyond dietary rules and represents *a specific lifestyle in all areas of work and behaviour* (Jašić et al., 2022), reflecting a holistic understanding of halal. This includes cleanliness, environmental awareness, fair treatment of workers and suppliers, and the overall way of conducting business. Some ethical issues associated with a holistic understanding of halal include responsible resource management, commitment to animal welfare standards, reducing environmental harm, ensuring the integrity of all stages in the food supply chain, and protecting consumer interests (Rahman et al., 2024). This list also includes issues regulated differently by the legal systems of various countries, such as worker exploitation, fraud, corruption, deception, false representation, forgery, bribery, conflicts of interest, and others.

The key question of the halal industry in achieving a holistic understanding of halal is whether companies need to meet only the technical requirements of halal standards or also need to adhere to the ethical principles associated with Islamic values and the nature of halal.

At first glance, the answer appears straightforward: the halal standard stipulates that a producer demonstrating the ability to meet the requirements and measures for all processes, products, or services aligned with Islamic rules qualifies for a halal quality certificate (BAS 1049, 2023). However, these provisions do not include ethical principles, meaning that adherence to ethical norms is not mandatory for producers. The separation of technical requirements from ethical expectations represents a critical challenge for the halal industry, which is ideally viewed as an inseparable combination of technical and ethical criteria. Consequently, as long as the halal status of a product is not compromised, certification bodies have no basis to suspend or revoke the halal certificate, regardless of the significance of the ethical principle involved.

The ethical dilemma intensifies when a halal-certified company deliberately violates an ethical principle, thereby jeopardizing trust in the halal industry. At that point, the halal certification body must decide whether to revoke the halal certificate for such a company. What mechanisms are available to halal certifiers to address this issue?

Resolving this dilemma starts from the premise that halal certification is voluntary (ISBIH, 2024), and significant ethical principles are still not thoroughly prescribed by halal standards²⁰. Certification requirements are primarily outlined by halal standards, and each company signs a halal certification agreement (Halal.ba - Certification, 2024). Based on the provisions of the OIC/SMIIC standard, the certification body can, through the certification agreement, obligate the company to adhere to specific, clearly defined ethical norms. This establishes legal grounds for suspending halal certificates when ethical principles are violated, not just when the halal status of a product is compromised²¹ (OIC/SMIIC 2, 2019).

However, if the producer has not contractually committed to ethical norms, the halal certification body lacks legal mechanisms for suspension. There is no clear consensus on whether the halal certification body must, can, or should revoke the halal certificate of an ethically compromised producer. Therefore, it is crucial for halal certification bodies to adopt clear guidelines that integrate the technical and ethical aspects of halal and include them in halal certification agreements. That will encompass all critical aspects of the holistic understanding of halal, maintain the integrity of the halal industry and ensure consumer trust.

Perception and Labelling of Halal Products

The markets of Balkan countries are characterized by the religious and cultural diversity of consumers and the absence of exclusive halal market niches. Halal consumers are present throughout the market, making it challenging to segment, group or separate halal products in retail outlets. A primary expectation of halal consumers is the ability to easily identify halal products. When this requirement is not met, distinguishing halal from non-halal products in retail becomes difficult.

²⁰ The OIC/SMIIC 18:2021 Halal Quality Management System – Requirements standard introduces the concept of ethical values in the halal industry. The adoption of a standard on the implementation of Islamic ethical principles and values in management systems is forthcoming. (<https://www.smiic.org/en/standards> – accessed on August 27, 2024.)

²¹ The Halal Certification Agreement is a legally enforceable arrangement signed between the applicant that has demonstrated compliance with halal requirements and the halal certification body/schema owner. This agreement governs the rules for the right to use the logo granted for halal products, services, processes, and/or management systems. (Clause 3.3, OIC/SMIIC 2:2019 Conformity Assessment – Requirements for Bodies Providing Halal Certification, Second Edition 2019-07-22)

Reading labels or memorizing information about all certified products is an overly complex task for consumers.

A straightforward solution is for all halal products to carry a halal label. However, this presents a significant challenge for some producers who must navigate diverse or even conflicting consumer expectations. From the perspective of a halal producer in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the dilemma surrounding halal product labelling is symbolically expressed in a question posed by a company from Sarajevo: "*What will our customers in Mostar and Banja Luka say?*" This question reflects concerns that Catholic and Orthodox customers (symbolized by Mostar and Banja Luka) might stop buying their products after certification and the application of a halal label.

Halal producers face the dilemma of balancing the need for Muslim consumers to recognize halal products while overcoming potential resistance and misunderstanding from non-Muslim consumers. The question arises: will the halal label on products be perceived by non-Muslims as an imposition of Islamic religious and ethical values?

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, this dilemma was resolved with the help of research on consumer attitudes towards halal product labelling. The research indicated that two-thirds of consumers across Bosnia and Herzegovina support labelling products with a halal logo (GMS, 2008). These results were encouraging and led the Halal Quality Certification Agency to decide on mandatory labelling of halal-certified products. The decision is codified in clause 12.1.2.1 of the Halal Standard, which establishes the principles for halal product labelling²² (BAS 1049, 2023). Exceptions to this labelling requirement are possible under certain conditions and with the Agency's approval (Halal.ba - Halal Logo, 2024). It is worth noting that some companies have no dilemmas regarding halal product labelling, as they consider it an integral part of the certification process.

The recent edition of BAS 1049:2023 is aligned with standard OIC-SMIIC 1 – Halal food (BAS 1049, 2023). This standard is used as a referential Halal standard across Balkan countries including Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro. In Croatia, the halal standard has been registered as HRN BAS 1049:2010 (HRN4You, 2010). This alignment of standard requirements provides a platform for a uniform

²² An identical provision is prescribed by the international halal standard OIC/SMIIC 1:2019 General Requirements for Halal Food, Clause 12.1.2.1. Labelling: "All Halal products should be appropriately labelled so that they can be identified and differentiated from non-Halal products. For certain products that are sold without packaging, it is possible to mark the point of sale."

The Malaysian Standard MS 1500:2019, Halal Food - Production, Preparation, Handling and Storage - General Guidelines (Third Revision), Clause 4.6.1 Storage, transportation, display, sale, and servings of halal food, states: "All halal food that are stored, transported, displayed, sold and/or served shall be categorised and labelled halal."

labelling system across the Balkan region.

Halal at a Higher Price

The implementation of halal standards imposes additional costs on producers, including the procurement of halal-compliant raw materials, investment in technology, employee training, and maintenance of the halal quality system. These factors can lead to increased product prices after halal certification, leaving producers with the dilemma of how consumers might respond to the adjusted pricing.

Producers face a choice of whether to raise prices and pass the additional costs to customers or maintain existing prices, effectively absorbing the costs and rewarding their customers. This pricing dilemma, caused by the costs of halal certification, can be examined from both the producer's and the consumer's perspective.

For halal producers, pricing decision is primarily driven by market dynamics and financial calculations. Certification provides access to a new market niche but raising prices risks alienating price-sensitive customers. On the other hand, maintaining current prices and absorbing the additional costs prioritizes customer satisfaction over profits. This suggests that producers are dealing with an economic rather than an ethical dilemma.

From the consumer's perspective, they may accept price increases as reasonable or view them as exploitative. According to European competition law, *price exploitation* is identified when prices have “no reasonable relation to the economic value of the product supplied” (Cleary Gottlieb, 2020). In this paper *price exploitation* refers to leveraging a monopolistic position, or the absence of competition within the halal market niche, to profit at the expense of halal consumers, who may feel obligated to continue purchasing halal products due to their religious commitment, despite the higher, unfair or excessive prices. Price-sensitive halal consumers may face an ethical dilemma: should they purchase halal products at a higher price or risk buying more affordable, non-halal-certified alternatives?

Understanding the concept of added value, the costs associated with quality assurance, and pricing strategies play a critical role in the market positioning of halal products. When the implementation of halal standards increases production costs, producers are entitled to decide whether to maintain current prices or increase them. This choice exposes producers to the risk of profit loss if the price remains unchanged or the possibility of a boycott by halal consumers if prices are significantly increased.

Alternatively, producers can mitigate potential negative reactions by transparent communication of the reasons behind price increases and promoting halal as an added value. Moderate price increases combined with adequate promotion of the product's added value can prevent consumer doubts about the ethical business practices of halal producers.

At the time of writing this paper, no data was available on the sensitivity of consumers in Balkan countries to price changes caused by the implementation of new quality standards. Therefore, it can only be hypothesized that halal consumers would consistently choose certified halal products, even at a higher price. Gathering empirical data on consumer sensitivity related to price fluctuation may guide producers in pricing strategies.

Halal Integrity and Non-Muslim Producers

The halal certification process can be considered as a technocratic procedure. According to the halal standard BAS 1049 and other SMIIC standards, the producer's adherence to Islam is not a requirement for halal certification. A producer who fulfils the requirements of the halal standard is entitled to receive a halal certificate.

However, obtaining a halal certificate does not guarantee instant trust among halal consumers. General perceptions, the prior reputation of the company and its owner, or even the location of production are external factors that may influence product acceptance. In regions where the traditional understanding of halal as a religious obligation is strong and where halal certification is a relatively new concept, the integrity, commitment, and dedication of non-Muslim producers could be questioned. Traditional halal consumers often express scepticism, questioning how the owner or workers of a company can sincerely adhere to principles that are not part of their religious beliefs and even they may not fully understand them.

Ensuring integrity and trust in products from non-Muslim producers is a key concern directed at halal certification bodies, which serve as mediators between halal producers and consumers. After accepting applications, halal certification bodies must ensure that non-Muslim producers thoroughly understand and genuinely commit to the ethical dimensions of halal production, which go beyond merely implementing the technical requirements of halal standards.

Prior to the halal certification, every company is required to adopt and make publicly available its commitment to halal. In this statement, the company voluntarily agrees to fulfil all halal requirements and establishes mechanisms within its organisational structure to ensure halal quality. At a minimum, companies must commit to meeting the requirements of the halal standard. Additionally, certification bodies may require companies to adopt Islamic Work Ethics, which are considered an essential component for both the company and their employees to prevent misconduct (OIC/SMIIC 2, 2019).

Halal certification is a voluntary process, and halal certification bodies do not have coercive mechanisms to mandate producers to undertake specific activities. This significantly weakens the authority of certification bodies and increases the risk of potential non-compliance. As a

result, certification bodies face the dilemma of whether to accept applications for

halal certification from companies that agree to meet all technical but not ethical principles of halal.

In such cases, any unethical behaviour by the halal-certified company or failure to adhere to ethical norms is attributed to the certification body. If an unethical act occurs, the company may face a loss of revenue due to reduced sales, while the certification body risks losing its reputation and bearing moral responsibility. This risk can be mitigated by incorporating critical ethical requirements into the halal certification agreement. Doing so ensures that both the producer and the certification body demonstrate a higher level of responsibility towards ethical principles and a commitment to adhering to them in their business practices.

Form, substance and halal product identity

A halal certification of products whose names and appearance resemble non-halal products is not available in certification practice in Balkan countries. These include items whose names contain references to alcoholic beverages like beer, champagne, or wine, as well as certain meat products traditionally made from non-halal animals.

When a product is primarily evaluated based on its ingredient list and production recipe, it fulfils the principle that combining and mixing halal ingredients results in a halal product. The form, appearance and name of the product do not alter its composition, meaning it remains halal. Thus, appearance, name, and manner of consumption are considered behavioural and ethical rather than technical issues of halal compliance.

Products that resemble or evoke associations with haram products, through their external characteristics, raise two dilemmas. The first pertains to the responsibility of halal certification bodies to decide whether such products should be certified. The second dilemma concerns halal consumers, who must determine whether they are willing to consume such products. The actions of both the certification bodies and the consumers largely depend on their understanding of halal and the extent to which Muslims identify with non-halal, even at the level of form or packaging appearance, rather than the product's content.

It is unknown whether any country explicitly prohibits the sale of halal beer, wine, or champagne. Similarly, the labelling and distribution policies for such products are not standardized globally. A useful example for regulating this issue within halal certification is provided by the Malaysian halal standard, which stipulates that halal products must not, through their appearance or names, contradict Islamic principles or confuse consumers. This also applies to generic or industrial ingredient names, which must not include terms identical to or synonymous with haram products (Standards Malaysia, 2019). In both cases, the standard uses the term "shall," indicating a mandatory requirement.

Whether others will follow Malaysia's example and how the halal industry will address these issues primarily depends on halal authorities, institutions responsible for halal standardisation, and other regulations governing the halal market. Adopting

the Malaysian model as a feasible solution could prevent confusion and misunderstanding among halal consumers and provide clear guidance for the halal industry.

CONCLUSION

The halal industry in the Balkan region is characterized by a blend of traditional and modern interpretations of halal principles. The market is open and inclusive, allowing voluntary participation by producers regardless of their religious affiliation. While the halal industry and certification system are well-regulated, certain ethical dilemmas require additional attention and consideration.

This paper elaborated on five ethical dilemmas that illustrate the complexity of understanding and implementing critical aspects of the halal industry. The labelling dilemma was addressed using the example of Bosnia and Herzegovina, where empirical data from consumer surveys helped resolve issues related to labelling products with halal logos. Provisions mandating labelling, as a part of the BAS 1049 standard, ensure consistency across the Balkan region.

The pricing dilemma highlighted the sensitivity of consumers to price increases which may discourage them from buying halal-certified products if prices rise significantly. In the absence of empirical research, it is suggested that producers promote halal as an added value to justify price adjustment.

Forms, names and symbols that associate with haram products remain inconsistently regulated on a global scale. The Malaysian standard is the only one that explicitly prohibits the use of non-halal terms and symbols on halal product packaging and may serve as a good example to amend other standards and regulations to prevent any confusion in identifying halal products.

Building trust in products from non-Muslim producers requires halal certification bodies to ensure compliance with halal standards through transparency and adequate halal education. Adherence to the key ethical principles can significantly increase halal consumer's trust.

The ethical dilemmas discussed in this study highlight the importance of adhering to both the halal standards and the principles of Islamic Work Ethics. The complexity of ethical dilemmas in the halal industry demands a greater focus on education and the continuous advancement of halal standards. All key stakeholders including certification bodies, producers, consumers, and regulatory authorities, must collaborate to maintain the integrity of the halal industry.

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